

Supporting Information

for

***N*-Sulfinylpyrrolidine-containing ureas and thioureas as bifunctional organocatalysts**

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Characterization data, copies of spectra, and DFT computational details

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1. General considerations

All commercially available chemicals were purchased from Merck, Alfa Aesar or TCI and were used without further purification. Solvents were distilled and dried according to the standard procedures. Thin-layer chromatography was performed on silica gel 60, F-254 nm plates. Compounds were visualized by irradiation with UV light and/or by treatment with KMnO_4 or *p*-anisaldehyde solution. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian NMR System 300 and Varian NMR System 600 (300 or 600 MHz for ^1H , 75 or 151 MHz for ^{13}C). Chemical shifts (δ ppm) are given in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane. Products of Michael additions were purified by flash chromatography using Isolera Biotage FSKO-1107-0010. Enantiomeric purity was determined by chiral HPLC column (Chiralcel AS-H, Chiralpak IC Chiralcel ODH). Specific optical rotations were measured on Jasco P-2000 polarimeter. High-resolution mass spectra were recorded with Thermo Velos Pro Orbitrap spectrometer. Melting points were measured on Büchi Melting Point M-565. Infrared spectroscopy spectra were recorded with Agilent Technologies Cary 630 FTIR. Frequencies are given in wavenumbers (cm^{-1}) and only selected peaks were reported. Mechanochemical reactions were carried out in a ball mill Retsch MM 400.

2. Characterization data

2-Ethyl-4-nitro-3-phenylbutanal (**8a**)[1]

Colourless oil, RF = 0.44 (Hexanes/EtOAc, 5:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.72 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 0.84H); 9.49 (d, $J = 2.9$ Hz, 0.16H); 7.36–7.28 (m, 3H); 7.19–7.17 (m, 2H); 4.83–4.75 (m, 0.32H); 4.72 (dd, $J = 12.7$; 4.9 Hz, 0.84H); 4.63 (dd, $J = 12.7$; 9.7 Hz, 0.84H); 3.79 (td, $J = 9.8$; 4.9 Hz, 1H); 2.7–2.66 (m, 1H); 1.54–1.49 (m, 2H); 0.99 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 0.5H); 0.84 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2.5H) ppm. **HPLC**: Chiralcel ODH, Hexane/iPrOH 80:20, 0.8 ml/min, $\lambda = 211$ nm, $t_{\text{R}} = 18.4$ min and 32.3 min (minor), $t_{\text{R}} = 17.1$ min and 21.0 min (major).

2-Ethyl-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-nitrobutanal (**8b**)[2]

Colourless oil, RF = 0.35 (Hexanes/EtOAc, 4:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 0.84 H); 9.47 (d, $J = 3$ Hz, 0.16 H); 7.09 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H); 6.87 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H); 4.8–4.71 (m, 0.32H); 4.69 (dd, $J = 12.6$; 4.9 Hz, 0.84H); 4.58 (dd, $J = 12.5$; 9.9 Hz, 0.84H); 3.79 (s, 2.5H); 3.78 (s, 0.5H); 3.74 (td, $J = 9.9$; 4.9 Hz, 1H); 2.65–2.61 (m, 1H); 1.55–1.47 (m, 2H); 0.99 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 0.5H); 0.83 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2.5H) ppm. **HPLC**: Chiralpak IC, Hexane/iPrOH 80:20, 1 ml/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm, $t_{\text{R}} = 18.2$ min and 23.8 min (minor), $t_{\text{R}} = 28.7$ min and 30.8 min (major).

2-[1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-nitroethyl]hexanal (**8c**)[3]

Colourless oil, RF = 0.36 (Hexanes/EtOAc, 4:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.70 (d, $J = 2.8$ Hz, 0.63H); 9.46 (d, $J = 3.1$ Hz, 0.37H); 7.08 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H); 6.87 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1H); 6.85 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1H); 4.78 (dd, $J = 12.8$; 6.0 Hz, 0.37H); 4.71 (dd, $J = 12.8$; 9.4 Hz, 0.37H); 4.67 (dd, $J = 12.6$; 5.0 Hz, 0.63H); 4.59 (dd, $J = 12.6$; 9.8 Hz, 0.63H); 3.79 (s, 1.1H); 3.78 (s, 1.9H); 3.74–3.70 (m, 1H); 2.67–2.62 (m, 0.63H); 2.60–2.56 (m, 0.37H); 1.52–1.37 (m, 2.4H); 1.26–1.12 (m, 3.6H); 0.89 (m, 1.1H); 0.79 (t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 1.9H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 203.5; 203.4; 159.3; 159.2; 129.3; 129.0; 128.5; 127.9; 114.5; 114.4; 78.7; 78.2; 55.22; 55.21; 54.0; 53.5; 43.8; 42.5; 29.1; 28.5; 27.3; 27.0; 22.6; 22.5; 13.8; 13.7 ppm. **HRMS (ESI)**: $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4$ calculated $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+ = 302.1363$, found 302.1362. **IR (ATR)**: 2930.2; 2859.8; 1719.0; 1610.9; 1549.3; 1512.7; 1464.0; 1377.8; 1249.5; 1179.6; 1032.2; 830.5;

755.6 cm^{-1} . **HPLC:** Chiralpak IC, Hexane/iPrOH 80:20, 1 ml/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm, $t_R = 15.0$ min and 20.8 min (minor), $t_R = 22.2$ min and 24.9 min (major).

2-[1-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2-nitroethyl]hexanal (**8d**)[3]

Colourless oil, RF = 0.36 (Hexanes/EtOAc, 4:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 0.8H); 9.48 (d, $J = 2.8$ Hz, 0.2H); 7.17–7.15 (m, 2H); 7.06–7.02 (m, 2H); 4.80 (dd, $J = 12.9$; 5.8 Hz, 0.2H); 4.75–4.71 (m, 0.2H); 4.70 (dd, $J = 12.8$; 4.8 Hz, 0.8H); 4.61 (dd, $J = 12.8$; 9.9 Hz, 0.8H); 3.77 (td, $J = 9.8$; 4.8 Hz, 1H); 2.70–2.65 (m, 0.8H); 2.64–2.60 (m, 0.2H); 1.49–1.45 (m, 1H); 1.43–1.38 (m, 1H); 1.26–1.22 (m, 2H); 1.18–1.13 (m, 2H); 0.90–0.89 (m, 0.6H), 0.79 (t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 2.4H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 203.0; 202.9; 162.3 (d, $J = 247.4$ Hz); 132.5 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz); 129.9 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz); 129.6 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz); 116.2 (d, $J = 21.5$ Hz); 116.1 (d, $J = 21.5$ Hz); 78.4; 77.9; 53.8; 53.5; 43.6; 42.4; 29.1; 28.4; 27.2; 27.0; 22.6; 22.5; 13.7; 13.6 ppm. **HRMS (ESI):** $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNO}_3$ calculated $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+ = 268.1343$, found 268.1352. **IR (ATR):** 2956.5; 2927.8; 2860.3; 1685.7 1636.9; 1458.2; 1413.5; 1378.4 1274.1; 1213.2; 933.4; 720.0; 659.7 cm^{-1} . **HPLC:** Chiralpak IC, Hexane/iPrOH 95:5, 1 ml/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm, $t_R = 18.7$ min and 28.6 min (minor), $t_R = 30.1$ min: and 35.4 min (major).

2-Benzyl-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-nitrobutanal (**8e**)

Colourless oil, RF = 0.35 (Hexanes/EtOAc, 3:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 0.8H); 9.55 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 0.2H); 7.32–7.24 (m, 2H); 7.21–7.19 (m, 1H); 7.13 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H); 7.09 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 0.4H); 7.03 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1.6H); 6.9 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1.6H); 6.87 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 0.4H); 4.84 (dd, $J = 13.0$, 6.3 Hz, 0.2 H), 4.75 (dd, $J = 12.9$, 9.1 Hz, 0,2 H), 4.70 (dd, $J = 12.7$, 5.4 Hz, 0,8 H), 4.65 (dd, $J = 12.6$, 9.3 Hz, 0,8 H); 3.81 (s, 2.4H); 3.80 (s, 0.6H); 3.79–3.75 (m, 1H); 3.09–2.99 (m, 1H); 2.76 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 202.2; 202.1; 158.4; 136.3; 136.2; 128.1; 127.9; 127.85; 127.8; 127.7; 127.35; 127.3; 126.0; 125.9; 113.6; 113.5; 77.3; 76.9; 54.5; 54.2; 53.4; 42.8; 41.8; 33.2; 32.7 ppm. **HRMS (ESI):** $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_4$ calculated $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^- = 312.1241$, found 312.1245. **IR (ATR):** 3026.6; 2925.8; 2836.5; 1719.6; 1610.0; 1548.6; 1512.4; 1540.0; 1438.1; 1377.7; 1249.5; 1179.3; 1029.8; 830.1; 749.4 cm^{-1} . **HPLC:** Chiralpak IC, Hexane/iPrOH 80:20, 1 ml/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm, $t_R = 15.6$ min and 20.8 min (minor), $t_R = 19.9$ min and 26.1 min (major).

2-Benzyl-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-4-nitrobutanal (**8f**)[3]

Colourless oil, $R_F = 0.34$ (Hexanes/EtOAc, 3:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.72 (d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, 0.62H); 9.55 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 0.38H); 7.23–7.18 (m, 5H); 7.08–7.04 (m, 2H); 7.02–7.01 (m, 2H); 4.85 (dd, $J = 13.1$; 6.2 Hz, 0.38H); 4.78 (dd, $J = 13.1$; 9.2 Hz, 0.38H); 4.72 (dd, $J = 12.8$; 5.2 Hz, 0.62H); 4.68 (dd, $J = 12.8$; 9.4 Hz, 0.62H); 3.82 (td, $J = 9.2$; 5.2 Hz, 1H); 3.12–3.07 (m, 1H); 2.8–2.73 (m, 2H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 202.8; 202.7; 162.42 (d, $J = 247.8$ Hz); 162.4 (d, $J = 247.9$ Hz); 137.0; 136.9; 132.5 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz); 131.6 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz); 130.2 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz); 129.7 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz); 128.9; 128.8; 128.7; 127.1; 127.0; 116.3 (d, $J = 21.5$ Hz); 116.1 (d, $J = 21.5$ Hz) 78.0; 77.7; 55.2; 54.3; 43.7; 42.7; 34.2 33.7 ppm. **HRMS (ESI):** $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{FNO}_3$ calculated $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+ = 302.1187$, found 302.1192. **IR (ATR):** 3026.2; 2921.7; 1720.8; 1602.6; 1553.7; 1509.8; 1453.8; 1377.5; 1225.3; 1161.0; 835.4; 746.5; 699.6 cm^{-1} . **HPLC:** Chiralpak IC, Hexane/iPrOH 80:20, 1 ml/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm, $t_R = 10.2$ min and 14.7 min (minor), $t_R = 13.3$ and 16.5 (major).

2-Benzyl-3-(furan-2-yl)-4-nitrobutanal (10a)[4]

Pale yellow oil, $R_F = 0.48$ (Hexanes/EtOAc, 3:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 1.1$ Hz, 0.75H); 9.69 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 0.25H); 7.40 (s, 1H); 7.34–7.27 (m, 2H); 7.25–7.22 (m, 1H); 7.15 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 0.5H); 7.12 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1.5H); 6.36–6.33 (m, 1H); 6.24–6.21 (m, 1H), 4.76–4.60 (m, 2H); 4.10–4.05 (m, 0.75H); 3.98–3.93 (m, 0.25H); 3.20–3.14 (m, 0.75H); 3.05 (dd, $J = 13.9$; 7.9 Hz, 0.25H); 3.00–2.95 (m, 0.25H); 2.88 (dd, $J = 14.4$; 8.9 Hz, 0.75H); 2.81 (dd, $J = 14.0$; 7.1 Hz, 0.25H); 2.76 (dd, $J = 14.4$; 5.6 Hz, 0.75H) ppm. **HPLC:** Chiralcel AS-H, heptane/iPrOH 90:10, 0.7 mL/min, $\lambda = 220$ nm, $t_R = 29.2$ min, $t_R = 39.5$ min.

3-(Furan-2-yl)-2-methyl-4-nitrobutanal (10b)[5]

Brown oil, $R_F = 0.32$ (Hexanes/EtOAc, 3:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 0.8$ Hz, 0.59H); 9.64 (d, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 0.41H); 7.37–7.36 (m, 1H); 6.32–6.3 (m, 1H); 6.2 (dd, $J = 12.6$; 3.3 Hz, 1H); 4.77–4.68 (m, 2H); 4.09 (dt, $J = 8.5$; 6.7 Hz, 0.59H); 4.01 (dt, $J = 8.8$; 5.6 Hz, 0.41H); 2.87–2.78 (m, 1H); 1.22 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1.75H); 1.08 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1.25H) ppm. **HPLC:** Chiralcel AS-H, Hexane/iPrOH 90:10, 0.8 ml/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm, $t_R = 23.1$ min and 27.8 min (minor), $t_R = 20.0$ min and 21.4 min (major).

2-[1-(Furan-2-yl)-2-nitroethyl]hexanal (10c)[3]

Brown oil, $R_F = 0.47$ ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{Hexanes}$, 3:1), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 0.5H); 9.6 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 0.5H); 7.37–7.36 (m, 1H); 6.32–6.30 (m, 1H); 6.21–6.19 (m, 1H); 4.78–4.62 (m, 2H); 4.04–3.93 (m, 1H); 2.78 (tdd, $J = 8.1$; 4.6; 1.9 Hz, 0.5H); 2.60 (dtd, $J = 8.3$; 5.4; 2.7 Hz, 0.5H); 1.74–1.64 (m, 1H); 1.55–1.44 (m, 2H); 1.35–1.28 (m, 3H); 0.89–0.85 (m, 3H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 202.3; 202.8; 150.1; 149.6; 142.7; 142.6; 110.5; 110.4; 108.9; 108.7; 76.1; 75.9; 52.2; 52.1; 38.0; 36.9; 29.2; 28.7; 26.9; 26.5; 22.6; 22.5; 13.7; 13.6 ppm. **HRMS (ESI)**: $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$ calculated $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+ = 240.1230$, found 240.1229. **IR (ATR)**: 2930.5; 2861.5; 2729.0; 1719.4; 1551.0; 1505.7; 1430.9; 1376.0; 1190.8; 1148.0; 1072.9; 1013.6; 913.7; 735.2 cm^{-1} . **HPLC**: Chiralpak IC, Hexane/iPrOH 95:5, 0.6 ml/min, $\lambda = 217$ nm, $t_R = 50.1$ min and 60.2 min (minor), $t_R = 44.8$ min and 57.3 (major).

2-Benzyl-4-nitro-3-(pyridin-3-yl)butanal (12)[6]

Pale yellow oil, $R_F = 0.21$ (Hexanes/EtOAc, 1:1), $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 3.58$ ($c = 0.5$, MeCN), $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.71 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 0.6H); 9.57 (d, $J = 1.1$ Hz, 0.4H), 8.58–8.53 (m, 1H); 8.48 (dd, $J = 9.8$ Hz; 1.9 Hz, 1H); 7.59–7.54 (m, 1H); 7.35–7.18 (m, 4H); 7.12 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H); 7.01 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H); 4.91–4.83 (m, 1H); 4.76 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 1H); 3.88–3.82 (m, 1H); 3.21–3.13 (m, 1H); 3.0 (dd, $J = 19.5$; 11.3 Hz, 0.6H); 2.85–2.74 (m, 2H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 202.3, 202.2, 150.0, 149.6, 149.51, 149.5, 136.5, 136.4, 136.1, 135.7, 132.8, 132.1, 129.1, 129.0, 128.73, 128.5, 128.3, 127.3, 127.2, 124.0, 123.9, 54.7, 54.1, 53.4, 41.6, 40.9, 34.2, 33.5 ppm. **IR (ATR)**: 1721.0; 1550.5; 1377.0; 1495.9 cm^{-1} . **HRMS (ESI)**: $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ calculated $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^- = 283.1077$, found 283.1088. **HPLC**: Chiralcel AS-H, hexane/iPrOH, 70:30, 0.75 mL/min, $\lambda = 218$ nm, $t_R = 27.0$ min and 29.2 (major), $t_R = 34.4$ and 43.4 min (minor).

3. Copies of ^1H , ^{13}C NMR and HRMS spectra

Figure S1. ^1H NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,R*)-5a

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,R*)-5a

sebesta_Nov_0202 #95-119 RT: 0.46-0.57 AV: 25 NL: 1.54E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-600.0000]

Figure S3. HRMS of *N*-Boc-(*S,R*)-5a

Figure S4. ¹H NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,S*)-5a

Figure S5. ¹³C NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,S*)-5a

Mar_22_004 #79-93 RT: 0.37-0.43 AV: 15 NL: 3.21E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-800.0000]

Figure S6. HRMS of *N*-Boc-(*S,S*)-5a

Figure S7. ^1H NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,R*)-5b

Figure S8. ^{13}C NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,R*)-5b

servis_Dec_13_010 #97-123 RT: 0.45-0.57 AV: 27 NL: 9.80E7
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-600.0000]

Figure S9. HRMS of *N*-Boc-(*S,R*)-5b

Figure S10. ¹H NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,S*)-5b

Figure S11. ¹³C NMR of *N*-Boc-(*S,S*)-5b

Mar_22_003 #80-100 RT: 0.37-0.47 AV: 21 NL: 6.45E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-800.0000]

Figure S12. HRMS of *N*-Boc-(*S,S*)-5b

Figure S13. ¹H NMR of (S,R)-C1

Figure S14. ¹³C NMR of (S,R)-C1

sebasta_Nov_0203 #102-117 RT: 0.52-0.59 AV: 16 SB: 21 0.25-0.35, 0.70 NL: 9.55E7
 T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-600.0000]

Figure S15. HRMS of (S,R)-C1

Figure S16. ¹H NMR of (S,S)-C1

Figure S17. ¹³C NMR of (S,S)-C1

Apr_18_001 #84-92 RT: 0.39-0.43 AV: 9 SB: 28 0.23-0.28, 0.60-0.67 NL: 7.29E7
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-900.0000]

Figure S18. HRMS1 of (S,S)-C1

Apr 18 005 #40-43 RT: 0.42-0.45 AV: 4 SB: 13 0.23-0.28, 0.63-0.69 NL: 1.07E7
T: FTMS - p ESI Full ms [100.0000-600.0000]

Figure S19. HRMS2 of (S,S)-C1

Figure S20. ¹H NMR of (S,R)-C2

Figure S21. ^{13}C NMR of (*S,R*)-C2

servis_Dec_13_011 #99-133 RT: 0.46-0.62 AV: 35 NL: 4.17E7
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-600.0000]

Figure S22. HRMS of (*S,R*)-C2

Figure S23. ^1H NMR of (S,S)-C2

Figure S24. ^{13}C NMR of (S,S)-C2

Apr_18_003 #75-79 RT: 0.35-0.37 AV: 5 SB: 25 0.22-0.26 , 0.59-0.65 NL: 6.40E6
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [100.0000-900.0000]

Figure S25. HRMS1 of (S,S)-C2

Apr_18_007 #37-43 RT: 0.40-0.46 AV: 7 SB: 19 0.22-0.30 , 0.54-0.64 NL: 1.62E7
T: FTMS - p ESI Full ms [100.0000-600.0000]

Figure S26. HRMS2 of (S,S)-C2

Figure S27. ¹H NMR of 8a

Figure S28. ¹H NMR of 8b

Figure S29. ¹H NMR of 8c

Figure S30. ¹³C NMR of 8c

Figure S31. ¹H NMR of 8d

Figure S32. ¹³C NMR of 8d

Figure S35. ¹H NMR of 8f

Figure S36. ¹³C NMR of 8f

Figure S37. ¹H NMR of 10a

Figure S38. ¹H NMR of 10b

Figure S41. ¹H NMR of 12

Figure S42. ¹³C NMR of 12

4. Copies of HPLC records

a) chiral

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area mAU	Area *s	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	17.145	BB	0.4454	69.50437		2.36074	17.8788
2	18.430	MM	0.3304	4.72392		2.38321e-1	1.2151
3	21.000	BB	0.5710	290.85626		7.61127	74.8177
4	32.264	MM	0.6692	23.66880		5.89492e-1	6.0884

b) racemic

Figure S43. HPLC trace of **8a**

Figure S44. HPLC trace of **8b** (racemic)

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S45. HPLC trace of **8c**

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S46. HPLC trace of **8d**

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S47. HPLC trace of **8e**

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S48. HPLC trace of 8f

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S49. HPLC trace of 10a

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S50. HPLC trace of 10b

a) chiral

b) racemic major

c) racemic minor

Figure S51. HPLC trace of 10c

a) chiral

b) racemic

Figure S52. HPLC trace of 12

5. Computational details

All calculations were realized using Turbomole program package [7,8]. Geometric optimizations were performed using PBEh-3c functional [9]. Geometrical optimizations were performed with def2-SV(P) basis set [10]. Energies were refined at M06-2X/def2-TZVP level [11,12].

3-phenylpropanal

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-422.9562016 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.134904 Hartree
Entropy	0.000152 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.179399 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	17.9533
In(Qrot)	13.4997
In(Qvib)	6.1921
ZPE	0.170448 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.180343 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-424.16538665 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

C	0.696695	-2.582738	-2.245463
H	1.641752	-2.766935	-2.818430
O	-0.237057	-3.317467	-2.361399
C	0.739445	-1.368415	-1.361337
C	-0.540423	-1.102125	-0.576966
C	-0.423104	0.124684	0.286059
C	-0.120195	2.422613	1.864623
C	0.069559	0.038291	1.587888
C	-0.763408	1.382895	-0.209735

C	-0.614458	2.522815	0.570018
C	0.220718	1.174893	2.371955
H	1.004899	-0.504923	-1.997132
H	1.605573	-1.481905	-0.685066
H	-0.777793	-1.979030	0.042751
H	0.333289	-0.938408	1.999165
H	0.603090	1.084380	3.389299
H	-0.005839	3.315665	2.479603
H	-0.891476	3.496574	0.164514
H	-1.159758	1.471953	-1.223441
H	-1.381509	-0.992817	-1.277006

Fur-nitroalkene

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-510.4688093 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.076329 Hartree
Entropy	0.000145 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.000145 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	18.0075
In(Qrot)	13.4168
In(Qvib)	4.8266
ZPE	0.110557 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.119502 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-511.93038572 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

C	0.024362	-0.000521	2.529793
C	1.379421	0.000113	2.402070
C	1.629610	0.000559	1.005012
C	0.403233	0.000177	0.396201
O	-0.562521	-0.000397	1.333051
C	0.050339	0.000040	-0.991377
C	-1.200050	0.000236	-1.466395

N	-1.450095	-0.000149	-2.889652
O	-2.605807	0.001863	-3.220584
O	-0.516213	-0.002513	-3.646148
H	0.885046	-0.000423	-1.694537
H	-2.106685	0.000843	-0.865422
H	2.592721	0.001087	0.502814
H	2.107136	0.000253	3.207557
H	-0.630497	-0.001166	3.397518

SR-cat (S,R)-C2

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1104.1083831 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.282091 Hartree
Entropy	0.000218 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.346062 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	18.8708
In(Qrot)	15.1125
In(Qvib)	15.2198
ZPE	0.328548 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.347007 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1106.5700552 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	0.397207	-1.097265	-3.018100
C	-0.664397	-2.073872	-2.890237
C	-1.801576	-1.246193	-2.309859
C	-1.659285	0.085458	-3.050828
C	-0.158704	0.195739	-3.403136
C	0.569894	1.316904	-2.661873
N	0.551866	1.079299	-1.243943
C	-0.080197	1.885573	-0.362784
O	-0.531517	2.973878	-0.615312
N	-0.167448	1.384791	0.948673

S	-0.042596	-0.252676	1.339535
O	-1.390247	-0.835674	1.542468
C	0.713068	-0.075989	3.024073
C	-0.213641	0.714098	3.935688
C	0.856879	-1.514708	3.518277
C	2.074556	0.583033	2.855930
H	-1.666187	-1.117033	-1.226420
H	-2.784995	-1.713654	-2.453999
H	-0.363488	-2.904857	-2.234339
H	-0.970463	-2.519620	-3.859950
H	-2.255480	0.073039	-3.974450
H	-2.018011	0.940956	-2.461446
H	1.170487	-1.397962	-3.596733
H	0.107462	2.289362	-2.873226
H	1.612828	1.377408	-3.018126
H	-0.751650	1.964868	1.545220
H	-0.045773	0.393015	-4.486691
H	0.834441	0.143889	-0.977403
H	1.339497	-1.516204	4.506684
H	2.708317	0.034800	2.142572
H	2.601954	0.591137	3.821551
H	1.484818	-2.118404	2.845448
H	1.992790	1.621398	2.509101
H	-1.232936	0.303696	3.927847
H	-0.258063	1.779910	3.669058
H	0.157214	0.664674	4.970423
H	-0.116624	-2.012817	3.616406

SS-cat (S,S)-C2

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1104.1113906 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.283467 Hartree
Entropy	0.000213 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.346045 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	18.8708
In(Qrot)	14.9653
In(Qvib)	14.2446

ZPE	0.328864 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.346989 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1106.57049853 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-0.929029	-1.612729	-0.631846
C	-2.275210	-1.113070	-0.886722
C	-2.151326	-0.523752	-2.282934
C	-1.231136	-1.518255	-2.989492
C	-0.286365	-2.024812	-1.884607
C	1.149108	-1.488920	-1.987478
N	1.290783	-0.084827	-2.290894
C	1.185304	0.988399	-1.442085
O	1.565297	2.089288	-1.750518
N	0.612989	0.687259	-0.217974
S	0.079664	1.968359	0.752927
O	-1.404385	1.886619	0.823968
C	0.700296	1.335397	2.384737
C	2.219752	1.291091	2.309201
C	0.233007	2.382783	3.393905
C	0.093556	-0.022379	2.697320
H	-1.694357	0.474730	-2.227267
H	-3.122898	-0.407990	-2.781043
H	-2.561365	-0.362495	-0.135991
H	-3.032086	-1.920720	-0.871074
H	-1.819028	-2.357107	-3.390480
H	-0.692083	-1.071770	-3.836054
H	-0.888681	-2.317826	0.092809
H	1.657079	-2.036153	-2.794147
H	1.693550	-1.750213	-1.062203
H	0.039410	-0.187425	-0.163925
H	-0.202906	-3.125292	-1.933247
H	1.739897	0.155474	-3.161524
H	0.588017	2.114468	4.400269
H	-1.003224	0.006350	2.634989
H	0.362889	-0.324797	3.721050
H	-0.862337	2.453548	3.429094
H	0.463383	-0.804580	2.019454
H	2.641206	2.257118	1.992628
H	2.573077	0.523638	1.607863
H	2.636384	1.058766	3.301246
H	0.631866	3.381725	3.159950

SR-cat starting materials complex

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3374171 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.508668 Hartree
Entropy	0.000381 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.621195 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.4328
In(Qvib)	43.5825
ZPE	0.585100 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.622139 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.24678927 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-2.251282	-0.138096	-1.989899
C	-3.508409	0.440351	-2.386599
C	-3.617368	0.052240	-3.858006
C	-2.167941	0.082962	-4.334947
C	-1.332732	-0.301025	-3.101868
C	-0.088315	0.586793	-2.994418
N	0.725108	0.354998	-1.834499
C	1.873764	-0.375020	-1.873546
O	2.285254	-0.936779	-2.858377
N	2.562396	-0.384174	-0.670493
S	3.941911	-1.342092	-0.459882
O	3.844625	-1.956362	0.890197
C	5.216832	-0.000187	-0.291850
C	4.926497	0.848112	0.935260
C	6.534391	-0.757250	-0.135256
C	5.204080	0.811201	-1.579862
C	-2.037359	-0.722819	-0.775470
C	-2.761934	-0.564310	0.348002

C	-2.540020	-1.345142	1.619783
C	-4.954182	2.619513	3.171729
C	-4.539144	3.651447	3.961058
C	-3.140537	3.741262	3.764821
C	-2.811383	2.755342	2.868914
O	-3.928253	2.085784	2.520239
C	-1.579454	2.326242	2.277386
C	-0.392552	2.892628	2.540717
N	0.810249	2.419039	1.922089
O	1.820662	3.013888	2.173433
O	0.750331	1.457826	1.189000
H	-0.223975	3.731325	3.212563
H	-1.636917	1.488869	1.571174
H	-2.457562	4.446808	4.229088
H	-5.932589	2.180241	2.993999
H	-5.159660	4.268270	4.603664
H	4.863593	0.233573	1.843472
H	5.737643	1.578277	1.080056
H	6.537015	-1.387933	0.763988
H	7.365658	-0.041763	-0.046765
H	6.068680	1.492319	-1.596378
H	6.743400	-1.398552	-1.005275
H	5.267983	0.171505	-2.472908
H	-3.508798	-1.739887	1.967400
H	-3.594867	0.144412	0.365720
H	-4.327921	0.026353	-1.778606
H	-4.028443	-0.965302	-3.938895
H	-4.274826	0.717078	-4.434801
H	-1.979301	-0.585371	-5.184977
H	-0.997454	-1.352294	-3.158634
H	-0.409136	1.641971	-2.990931
H	-1.901299	1.099111	-4.668640
H	-3.536911	1.539619	-2.252393
H	-2.205111	-0.672513	2.430491
H	-1.186528	-1.410392	-0.766616
H	2.215681	0.124507	0.139395
H	4.298624	1.425995	-1.670081
H	0.530024	0.440637	-3.890743
H	3.994219	1.423328	0.843929
H	0.417268	0.749746	-0.958221
C	-1.563926	-2.481114	1.482753
C	0.257002	-4.571664	1.083431
C	-0.191288	-2.266098	1.599531
C	-2.009360	-3.764008	1.167166
C	-1.108736	-4.803658	0.974311
C	0.717451	-3.298158	1.395766
H	0.178986	-1.267804	1.841698
H	-3.080656	-3.950212	1.066885
H	-1.477012	-5.801584	0.732369
H	0.967096	-5.383659	0.923568

H 1.786818 -3.098350 1.464888

SS-cat starting materials complex

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3371845 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.509657 Hartree
Entropy	0.000374 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620248 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.4656
In(Qvib)	42.4366
ZPE	0.585038 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621192 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.24915538 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.281975	0.925343	-2.140187
C	-2.695916	1.190042	-2.237611
C	-2.984592	1.032066	-3.726369
C	-1.693672	1.508721	-4.381173
C	-0.584088	1.093273	-3.406192
C	0.530030	2.146321	-3.379450
N	1.592849	1.887065	-2.447181
C	2.500983	0.897999	-2.651072
O	2.599907	0.274662	-3.680523

N	3.290262	0.628464	-1.543881
S	4.641211	-0.397072	-1.659741
O	5.748295	0.273920	-0.938430
C	4.060051	-1.764299	-0.539656
C	2.824626	-2.386121	-1.175066
C	5.223300	-2.753824	-0.525773
C	3.788890	-1.223279	0.853917
C	-0.726400	0.303789	-1.064571
C	-1.279075	0.073537	0.142241
C	-0.586877	-0.727094	1.204101
C	-4.167139	2.896394	4.518361
C	-3.304793	2.301267	5.391032
C	-2.072536	2.202362	4.701087
C	-2.281507	2.747514	3.459659
O	-3.560249	3.162763	3.367080
C	-1.451455	2.934285	2.307869
C	-0.162616	2.577208	2.244349
N	0.579452	2.721991	1.028532
O	1.662194	2.186873	0.998631
O	0.109723	3.346892	0.115395
H	0.405342	2.104399	3.042221
H	-1.921438	3.379498	1.428162
H	-1.143922	1.779213	5.073295
H	-5.214734	3.175475	4.599050
H	-3.526904	1.973559	6.401854
H	3.005015	-2.688195	-2.217273
H	2.527893	-3.284340	-0.612363
H	5.460330	-3.120746	-1.536311
H	4.959332	-3.628695	0.087145
H	3.566428	-2.055471	1.539459
H	6.132770	-2.306818	-0.102524
H	4.659341	-0.683917	1.252499
H	-0.553197	-0.167394	2.153833
H	-2.290142	0.420617	0.371951
H	-3.265966	0.474138	-1.624674
H	-3.164429	-0.028564	-3.957937
H	-3.869583	1.592805	-4.056655
H	-1.536078	1.094234	-5.385542
H	-0.137919	0.132594	-3.719661
H	0.096515	3.120562	-3.111801
H	-1.708324	2.605748	-4.488915
H	-2.958456	2.202098	-1.874021
H	0.465711	-0.886930	0.915163
H	0.292460	-0.055960	-1.236745
H	3.213571	1.186955	-0.698012
H	2.921062	-0.548713	0.876213
H	0.939860	2.240952	-4.396711
H	1.967134	-1.699694	-1.170340
H	1.534586	2.340524	-1.547924
C	-1.233711	-2.066955	1.472940

C	-2.425616	-4.560065	1.952540
C	-1.333836	-3.018727	0.457300
C	-1.746035	-2.384683	2.727651
C	-2.339440	-3.619552	2.969067
C	-1.917986	-4.254428	0.693452
H	-0.950759	-2.781035	-0.537197
H	-1.681557	-1.650682	3.534093
H	-2.736811	-3.846213	3.959284
H	-2.888663	-5.529807	2.137789
H	-1.981126	-4.986848	-0.112436

TS-major-si-SR-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: *PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)*

SFC energy	-1961.3235111 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.519363 Hartree
Entropy	0.000345 Hartree
Inner energy	0.621267 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.2619
In(Qvib)	35.1157
ZPE	0.587639 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.622211

Single point energy: *M06-2X/def2-TZVP*

SCF energy	-1966.23666674 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.730925	0.372242	-1.807458
C	-3.172149	0.462988	-1.969327
C	-3.410901	-0.154080	-3.338959
C	-2.182951	0.281988	-4.127499
C	-1.039242	0.295853	-3.107363
C	-0.060560	1.441623	-3.396835
N	1.044079	1.551134	-2.491153
C	2.006608	0.601407	-2.437081

O	2.124226	-0.299206	-3.232270
N	2.861524	0.736484	-1.336834
S	3.506767	-0.699019	-0.711554
O	2.644301	-1.130998	0.424659
C	5.047242	0.003871	0.042019
C	4.717124	1.075905	1.068939
C	5.704571	-1.202288	0.712189
C	5.908286	0.529444	-1.098539
C	-1.128985	0.153482	-0.649545
C	-1.710979	0.075594	0.621630
C	-0.959488	-0.735596	1.653651
C	-4.804379	1.560181	3.155680
C	-4.040142	1.450306	4.273501
C	-2.695628	1.617529	3.837952
C	-2.750888	1.819363	2.487509
O	-4.035911	1.779971	2.084391
C	-1.736892	2.019942	1.466500
C	-0.437157	2.346012	1.869008
N	0.484224	2.666581	0.916476
O	1.664729	2.790318	1.205005
O	0.089510	2.795449	-0.252524
H	-0.039248	2.184180	2.866656
H	-2.103205	2.475783	0.546547
H	-1.800413	1.603193	4.451752
H	-5.877399	1.512459	2.989504
H	-4.391155	1.277183	5.286174
H	3.967575	0.729871	1.793491
H	5.627858	1.337976	1.628995
H	5.081344	-1.610894	1.518775
H	6.666700	-0.897884	1.149901
H	6.894186	0.825409	-0.709415
H	5.910912	-2.010503	-0.006088
H	6.075115	-0.234437	-1.872955
H	-1.260148	-0.416657	2.664311
H	-2.798389	-0.038984	0.645729
H	-3.689418	-0.072407	-1.162462
H	-3.449216	-1.250160	-3.251584
H	-4.356038	0.172767	-3.791561
H	-1.958762	-0.372963	-4.978885
H	-0.480470	-0.651894	-3.142808
H	-0.602779	2.397924	-3.373463
H	-2.335867	1.294660	-4.534980
H	-3.503456	1.514629	-1.928659
H	0.120261	-0.543684	1.567027
H	-0.054440	-0.031879	-0.717595
H	2.651516	1.460233	-0.647852
H	5.459917	1.407735	-1.580825
H	0.299324	1.301780	-4.428117
H	4.347140	2.003429	0.611956
H	0.901839	2.168161	-1.688118

C	-1.232044	-2.211893	1.500424
C	-1.808324	-4.928276	1.133981
C	-0.317731	-3.050739	0.864110
C	-2.433795	-2.754737	1.956992
C	-2.722437	-4.100893	1.776264
C	-0.605993	-4.398668	0.682474
H	0.637508	-2.646464	0.522621
H	-3.154181	-2.112543	2.469977
H	-3.664666	-4.508707	2.144911
H	-2.030663	-5.986578	0.992934
H	0.122733	-5.042203	0.187999

TS-major-re-SR-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3240405 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.520006 Hartree
Entropy	0.000343 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.621207 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.2407
In(Qvib)	34.5162
ZPE	0.587696 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.622151 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.24273958 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.168501	0.274731	-1.815880
C	-2.557560	0.542212	-2.162412
C	-2.756166	-0.288261	-3.421153
C	-1.430316	-0.097391	-4.154169
C	-0.375831	0.100752	-3.049147
C	0.551895	1.275762	-3.374320
N	1.529517	1.551753	-2.364847
C	2.444116	0.623495	-1.994583
O	2.697176	-0.367617	-2.637649

N	3.046879	0.895026	-0.766560
S	3.798506	-0.425253	-0.015040
O	2.784053	-1.149225	0.800638
C	4.826890	0.544145	1.187525
C	3.950967	1.383478	2.105854
C	5.559539	-0.534045	1.986025
C	5.810001	1.384960	0.384074
C	-0.762446	-0.187897	-0.642847
C	-1.539295	-0.323602	0.508931
C	-0.932716	-1.087179	1.665313
C	-4.935464	0.874468	2.848518
C	-5.517418	1.559823	1.830304
C	-4.446567	2.006628	1.005415
C	-3.296358	1.559589	1.593124
O	-3.606072	0.871934	2.706759
C	-1.890785	1.647073	1.225614
C	-1.521660	2.623461	0.295415
N	-0.201594	2.800272	0.009052
O	0.144088	3.636489	-0.824683
O	0.622290	2.075966	0.575503
H	-2.213376	3.225554	-0.286329
H	-4.521963	2.595223	0.096007
H	-5.337586	0.361905	3.718329
H	-6.579853	1.732254	1.687617
H	3.162173	0.779279	2.574453
H	4.568267	1.810381	2.911000
H	4.862773	-1.169842	2.548556
H	6.239978	-0.058069	2.707695
H	6.535208	1.856030	1.064821
H	6.168508	-1.182555	1.337703
H	6.380375	0.774035	-0.331782
H	-1.423715	-0.785305	2.602660
H	-2.606160	-0.500655	0.349346
H	-3.237650	0.286635	-1.341564
H	-2.909975	-1.343562	-3.149757
H	-3.625616	0.030865	-4.010828
H	-1.177019	-0.940398	-4.808997
H	0.236711	-0.802939	-2.932215
H	-0.042658	2.190741	-3.508135
H	-1.478651	0.797248	-4.794864
H	-2.689303	1.615466	-2.371436
H	0.129398	-0.819031	1.762376
H	0.294995	-0.462682	-0.589743
H	2.514432	1.511949	-0.147721
H	5.308028	2.183317	-0.177487
H	1.025866	1.056088	-4.345207
H	3.475260	2.228835	1.589619
H	1.383281	2.388348	-1.807948
C	-1.077910	-2.577755	1.484093
C	-1.400069	-5.325246	1.047942

C	-0.023459	-3.345155	0.989716
C	-2.291549	-3.207186	1.762562
C	-2.454607	-4.569009	1.546429
C	-0.185650	-4.708834	0.773697
H	0.938900	-2.871752	0.783898
H	-3.122469	-2.620762	2.162290
H	-3.409352	-5.044891	1.774554
H	-1.523752	-6.395744	0.880252
H	0.650844	-5.295458	0.391982
H	-1.181669	1.431993	2.027114

TS-minor-SR-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3152305 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.517947 Hartree
Entropy	0.000348 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620700 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.2754
In(Qvib)	35.8387
ZPE	0.586918 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621644 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.23002198 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.787421	1.016079	-1.084338
C	-2.960392	1.857950	-0.914104
C	-3.267344	2.298688	-2.338472
C	-1.891694	2.393516	-3.011039
C	-0.947081	1.518515	-2.169580
C	0.231061	2.337732	-1.615697
N	1.119482	1.617073	-0.745779
C	2.112831	0.829200	-1.256596

O	2.353378	0.750722	-2.434625
N	2.843994	0.142018	-0.306444
S	3.813055	-1.185683	-0.779840
O	3.597040	-2.236461	0.245568
C	5.493132	-0.477592	-0.432746
C	5.625685	-0.135523	1.041058
C	6.452474	-1.599664	-0.826724
C	5.675695	0.737169	-1.331689
C	-1.422421	0.010976	-0.325402
C	-2.185838	-0.534083	0.721788
C	-1.416623	-1.445787	1.655639
C	-5.711073	-2.214039	2.519000
C	-6.531438	-1.320418	1.910599
C	-5.860201	-0.932448	0.714476
C	-4.685326	-1.626480	0.690556
O	-4.602656	-2.396025	1.790280
C	-3.551764	-1.648186	-0.239237
C	-3.815984	-1.191476	-1.546266
N	-2.854015	-1.308120	-2.514221
O	-3.062354	-0.879575	-3.641215
O	-1.777206	-1.819866	-2.196609
H	-4.728886	-0.685234	-1.846426
H	-2.926987	-2.542895	-0.161810
H	-6.216170	-0.235805	-0.038560
H	-5.792774	-2.785590	3.439515
H	-7.501361	-0.983868	2.264167
H	5.442359	-1.011682	1.677578
H	6.646890	0.219309	1.248727
H	6.299887	-2.501201	-0.217981
H	7.491167	-1.267504	-0.681676
H	6.721390	1.076863	-1.282066
H	6.342491	-1.877855	-1.885956
H	5.448620	0.511240	-2.383856
H	-1.094350	-2.346005	1.109042
H	-2.876539	0.156191	1.214502
H	-3.780963	1.312408	-0.438284
H	-3.875716	1.534455	-2.838626
H	-3.823820	3.244362	-2.367907
H	-1.928338	2.047936	-4.050100
H	-0.566430	0.657884	-2.739070
H	-0.157690	3.207914	-1.063480
H	-1.530939	3.433528	-3.029406
H	-2.708570	2.719347	-0.265920
H	-2.084096	-1.805197	2.452997
H	-0.480360	-0.464305	-0.596950
H	2.599816	0.170571	0.681446
H	5.039782	1.577940	-1.024591
H	0.799603	2.732987	-2.468953
H	4.936991	0.667644	1.341397
H	0.915058	1.591961	0.243665

C	-0.198875	-0.791734	2.270008
C	2.075692	0.419821	3.392902
C	-0.250243	0.515374	2.767096
C	1.014009	-1.473279	2.341188
C	2.139525	-0.879636	2.906496
C	0.872767	1.117853	3.318851
H	-1.186541	1.074398	2.725499
H	1.098741	-2.480146	1.931080
H	3.073432	-1.439451	2.939147
H	2.957537	0.887497	3.832367
H	0.806791	2.135789	3.705407

TS-minor-re-SR-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.310462744 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.517148 Hartree
Entropy	0.000349 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620277 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.2885
In(Qvib)	36.0136
ZPE	0.586297 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621221 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.223109725 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.948672	1.211631	-1.117280
C	-3.253957	1.840942	-1.051595
C	-3.455479	2.308215	-2.486823
C	-2.055244	2.757037	-2.905045
C	-1.093637	1.860861	-2.108080

C	0.018194	2.674710	-1.431473
N	0.918008	1.903672	-0.619026
C	1.977708	1.245769	-1.176758
O	2.245622	1.301075	-2.351019
N	2.740700	0.529244	-0.276609
S	3.830376	-0.664569	-0.833508
O	3.688813	-1.810770	0.098276
C	5.435037	0.155105	-0.386045
C	5.504892	0.387814	1.113220
C	6.497746	-0.844401	-0.839743
C	5.529243	1.450028	-1.181061
C	-1.590516	0.105269	-0.503729
C	-2.306648	-0.581336	0.496079
C	-1.465036	-1.478898	1.373237
C	-6.129512	-1.750862	1.973588
C	-5.712759	-3.004312	2.284467
C	-4.636146	-3.286322	1.393709
C	-4.488516	-2.181195	0.608170
O	-5.395602	-1.253055	0.969628
C	-3.561447	-1.822082	-0.465818
C	-2.866599	-2.867086	-1.095984
N	-2.102801	-2.588604	-2.202715
O	-1.513415	-3.480384	-2.779243
O	-2.024995	-1.405153	-2.562058
H	-2.802878	-3.885612	-0.723782
H	-3.948595	-1.044140	-1.128480
H	-4.052986	-4.200075	1.335971
H	-6.917903	-1.115608	2.368396
H	-6.124565	-3.653849	3.051010
H	5.371873	-0.546992	1.674322
H	6.490867	0.798783	1.379303
H	6.413795	-1.801076	-0.306756
H	7.499561	-0.435132	-0.642088
H	6.539238	1.874442	-1.073878
H	6.433700	-1.046469	-1.919840
H	5.347131	1.290995	-2.253915
H	-1.082984	-2.319061	0.769364
H	-3.055138	0.018789	1.022341
H	-4.022068	1.138655	-0.708116
H	-3.786769	1.458318	-3.100644
H	-4.209279	3.101560	-2.574867
H	-1.887841	2.672005	-3.985614
H	-0.643107	1.084018	-2.744178
H	-0.436742	3.451454	-0.796854
H	-1.897823	3.815357	-2.641094
H	-3.244183	2.691464	-0.345273
H	-2.109924	-1.937671	2.140350
H	-0.611997	-0.278399	-0.796851
H	2.481806	0.457082	0.705179
H	4.814465	2.205053	-0.827915

H	0.588989	3.195328	-2.213265
H	4.750317	1.112364	1.452453
H	0.689308	1.758676	0.355185
C	-0.300854	-0.789447	2.047508
C	1.871047	0.470256	3.314037
C	-0.428278	0.494606	2.588799
C	0.937267	-1.421449	2.145583
C	2.011035	-0.805573	2.782012
C	0.644184	1.121171	3.211456
H	-1.385725	1.014782	2.528248
H	1.081140	-2.407266	1.701674
H	2.966991	-1.325463	2.832217
H	2.712570	0.956042	3.809266
H	0.518701	2.120041	3.631776

TS-major-si-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: *PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)*

SFC energy	-1961.3180557 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.515745 Hartree
Entropy	0.000355 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620712 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.3117
In(Qvib)	38.0181
ZPE	0.586809 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621656 Hartree

Single point energy: *M06-2X/def2-TZVP*

SCF energy	-1966.22974711 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.238731	1.112187	-1.877240
C	-2.609441	1.494461	-2.179333

C	-2.732922	1.216065	-3.669917
C	-1.343480	1.550260	-4.195660
C	-0.385520	1.121573	-3.081281
C	0.831475	2.050443	-3.009143
N	1.814162	1.717537	-2.023425
C	2.640903	0.652384	-2.166505
O	2.676157	-0.050308	-3.148230
N	3.425178	0.415240	-1.042446
S	4.661867	-0.748489	-1.111721
O	5.970795	-0.067084	-1.005436
C	4.361517	-1.536366	0.547672
C	2.947803	-2.098582	0.549919
C	5.394247	-2.661246	0.603782
C	4.592694	-0.534187	1.667059
C	-0.843970	0.631650	-0.714819
C	-1.602721	0.485931	0.458827
C	-1.152870	-0.599912	1.410729
C	-4.723351	2.181298	2.799065
C	-4.167915	1.784984	3.973397
C	-2.764980	1.730680	3.736269
C	-2.580136	2.102681	2.434820
O	-3.775693	2.370709	1.874931
C	-1.402592	2.218845	1.586045
C	-0.143345	2.215881	2.205661
N	0.964796	2.456086	1.448395
O	2.084173	2.311562	1.911955
O	0.792572	2.796004	0.266939
H	0.048399	1.862936	3.214973
H	-1.530398	2.881141	0.728594
H	-1.989423	1.466991	4.448859
H	-5.749801	2.371224	2.496579
H	-4.691664	1.566143	4.898899
H	2.753261	-2.726298	-0.333545
H	2.793943	-2.727507	1.439708
H	5.262707	-3.380285	-0.219347
H	5.287293	-3.216219	1.547576
H	4.560364	-1.051823	2.638218
H	6.420299	-2.272351	0.556645
H	5.576931	-0.054665	1.577359
H	-1.523652	-0.379340	2.423733
H	-2.686998	0.555943	0.333274
H	-3.317774	0.913245	-1.573921
H	-2.966540	0.153472	-3.833742
H	-3.529875	1.803585	-4.143696
H	-1.106424	1.054925	-5.145702
H	-0.026451	0.094925	-3.256683
H	0.490769	3.076127	-2.805280
H	-1.255303	2.635113	-4.369680
H	-2.774711	2.559180	-1.943977
H	-0.053966	-0.599696	1.478499

H	0.190772	0.282608	-0.699877
H	3.474139	1.117540	-0.306574
H	3.822750	0.250266	1.704600
H	1.284975	2.055722	-4.012508
H	2.193998	-1.299580	0.576211
H	1.728234	2.195242	-1.124303
C	-1.646632	-1.961322	0.989632
C	-2.627364	-4.445003	0.137898
C	-0.902749	-2.763969	0.125111
C	-2.888688	-2.424430	1.421674
C	-3.377296	-3.654942	1.000110
C	-1.386340	-3.995438	-0.297431
H	0.076425	-2.425855	-0.220568
H	-3.481864	-1.812079	2.104709
H	-4.349168	-4.001814	1.353004
H	-3.006728	-5.412884	-0.190701
H	-0.785920	-4.610713	-0.968437

TS-major-re-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3162281 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.51645 Hartree
Entropy	0.000352 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620591 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.3228
In(Qvib)	37.1549
ZPE	0.586710 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621535 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.23161921 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-0.889895	0.977455	-1.722546
C	-2.198286	1.180730	-2.339368

C	-1.988610	0.701798	-3.767195
C	-0.572921	1.177728	-4.063787
C	0.183356	1.005889	-2.743352
C	1.231471	2.103329	-2.550174
N	2.043702	1.961036	-1.377562
C	3.021396	1.026546	-1.303509
O	3.381791	0.343612	-2.235004
N	3.558128	0.872962	-0.034999
S	5.050566	0.069297	0.190997
O	5.760957	0.841131	1.237680
C	4.436981	-1.471953	1.027892
C	3.632920	-1.110552	2.264493
C	3.623473	-2.251466	0.004627
C	5.710419	-2.227876	1.400604
C	-0.699670	0.490731	-0.511185
C	-1.683311	0.269569	0.462502
C	-1.276924	-0.557615	1.663734
C	-5.361838	1.157932	2.521401
C	-5.872281	1.810932	1.445711
C	-4.748628	2.324063	0.737026
C	-3.642906	1.945173	1.443658
O	-4.026216	1.234804	2.519722
C	-2.209976	2.120335	1.222210
C	-1.825778	3.182756	0.392324
N	-0.502375	3.470221	0.233849
O	-0.152002	4.392239	-0.486775
O	0.321765	2.744427	0.813893
H	-2.509748	3.786511	-0.197048
H	-4.762842	2.907927	-0.178413
H	-5.821881	0.620941	3.346590
H	-6.922104	1.921196	1.191393
H	2.691276	-0.603261	2.009116
H	3.370386	-2.023052	2.821783
H	2.704139	-1.726285	-0.286051
H	3.330554	-3.224190	0.429159
H	5.447546	-3.193846	1.857349
H	4.194947	-2.446088	-0.914389
H	6.333008	-2.442481	0.518225
H	-1.966891	-0.360623	2.496643
H	-2.686458	0.058077	0.082249
H	-2.979796	0.631161	-1.799227
H	-2.052310	-0.396162	-3.812732
H	-2.737798	1.105074	-4.460848
H	-0.087497	0.628368	-4.880213
H	0.693012	0.029906	-2.724197
H	0.739891	3.084068	-2.501269
H	-0.585380	2.240812	-4.353658
H	-2.467518	2.246537	-2.314646
H	-0.283419	-0.229206	2.006112
H	0.342356	0.273477	-0.265742

H	3.291515	1.495861	0.722788
H	6.320995	-1.667896	2.121217
H	1.865763	2.101894	-3.449360
H	4.205104	-0.460382	2.940984
H	1.741617	2.461953	-0.545759
C	-1.263367	-2.035811	1.369358
C	-1.261595	-4.764843	0.726183
C	-0.072488	-2.703606	1.091693
C	-2.454956	-2.760398	1.327137
C	-2.456259	-4.111680	1.008213
C	-0.068469	-4.055746	0.771105
H	0.872882	-2.159824	1.135020
H	-3.398455	-2.258508	1.553366
H	-3.397620	-4.661975	0.984895
H	-1.261312	-5.826399	0.477844
H	0.876268	-4.557996	0.559125
H	-1.581824	1.930265	2.096011

TS-minor-si-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: *PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)*

SFC energy	-1961.3162133 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.519481 Hartree
Entropy	0.000343 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620676 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.1698
In(Qvib)	34.3804
ZPE	0.586976 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621620 Hartree

Single point energy: *M06-2X/Def2-TZVP*

SCF energy	-1966.23102434 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.295277	1.548393	-0.673200
C	-2.520487	2.303809	-0.404787
C	-2.477012	3.466275	-1.398005
C	-1.511283	2.994673	-2.484103
C	-0.482811	2.169407	-1.720369
C	0.653664	3.013595	-1.115610
N	1.586340	2.237313	-0.345023
C	2.535525	1.478656	-0.979996
O	2.879038	1.673110	-2.119056
N	3.038960	0.445204	-0.223368
S	4.459954	-0.387774	-0.691019
O	5.109403	-0.768656	0.589096
C	3.726678	-1.950004	-1.380585
C	4.953559	-2.790190	-1.734246
C	2.871112	-2.639605	-0.333897
C	2.930461	-1.595965	-2.628979
C	-0.891683	0.519619	0.031259
C	-1.677246	-0.142344	0.993734
C	-0.904358	-1.018151	1.962301
C	-5.136245	-2.251854	2.406520
C	-6.002155	-1.433325	1.756949
C	-5.282460	-0.918689	0.639434
C	-4.036264	-1.470906	0.697924
O	-3.956016	-2.272955	1.774725
C	-2.832661	-1.328814	-0.126974
C	-3.028559	-0.845624	-1.438917
N	-1.981920	-0.831780	-2.317516
O	-2.127875	-0.380277	-3.444094
O	-0.889226	-1.256374	-1.919284
H	-3.954274	-0.410571	-1.804599
H	-2.131425	-2.163473	-0.031866
H	-5.652514	-0.235004	-0.118525
H	-5.228034	-2.868379	3.296591
H	-7.031769	-1.226847	2.033122
H	5.550938	-3.042730	-0.847835
H	4.628909	-3.730615	-2.203500
H	3.416943	-2.779683	0.609656
H	2.571378	-3.633318	-0.699705
H	2.646176	-2.522940	-3.149445
H	1.945076	-2.081093	-0.137210
H	1.995846	-1.067285	-2.401397
H	-0.566193	-1.932985	1.449543
H	-2.469841	0.459556	1.447699
H	-3.398127	1.664291	-0.551761
H	-3.473487	3.703944	-1.790947
H	-2.105328	4.378415	-0.908945
H	-2.022602	2.345550	-3.208585
H	-0.049247	1.380014	-2.352603
H	0.246376	3.807930	-0.471738
H	-1.053647	3.820816	-3.044600

H	-2.534800	2.643376	0.644045
H	-1.577475	-1.361826	2.761530
H	0.093717	0.127645	-0.213387
H	2.723016	0.257904	0.726011
H	3.510682	-0.982313	-3.332523
H	1.187762	3.510818	-1.936188
H	5.607735	-2.275923	-2.455193
H	1.387471	2.071461	0.632250
C	0.303835	-0.333650	2.563728
C	2.595058	0.952036	3.567830
C	0.255195	0.999024	2.983705
C	1.517163	-1.010739	2.680495
C	2.655754	-0.378127	3.172363
C	1.385925	1.635044	3.482795
H	-0.682189	1.554395	2.917950
H	1.582411	-2.051906	2.361458
H	3.601341	-0.918344	3.211345
H	3.488075	1.454220	3.939508
H	1.323111	2.674845	3.806416

TS-minor-si-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3167839 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.51997 Hartree
Entropy	0.00034 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.620485 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.1456
In(Qvib)	33.7004
ZPE	0.5868 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.621429 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.229824173 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.334573	1.788056	-0.793096
C	-2.622127	2.448197	-0.626418
C	-2.491644	3.736198	-1.435874
C	-1.421342	3.404234	-2.474530
C	-0.453440	2.498640	-1.719113
C	0.637237	3.279391	-0.962535
N	1.504313	2.431241	-0.193908
C	2.480187	1.699664	-0.822656
O	2.887134	1.962898	-1.927048
N	2.922099	0.613718	-0.106265
S	4.329360	-0.255849	-0.553206
O	4.902971	-0.719893	0.735694
C	3.558457	-1.749151	-1.345994
C	4.759770	-2.624481	-1.701566
C	2.640269	-2.452299	-0.364109
C	2.826001	-1.296355	-2.600674
C	-0.991825	0.672243	-0.188325
C	-1.783831	-0.056432	0.719469
C	-1.022819	-0.907248	1.710896
C	-5.733439	-1.411474	1.541475
C	-5.305884	-2.633184	1.949357
C	-4.082461	-2.865854	1.256197
C	-3.867368	-1.766112	0.478059
O	-4.871357	-0.887305	0.660682
C	-2.794266	-1.372612	-0.434587
C	-1.942038	-2.387626	-0.901856
N	-1.017959	-2.101728	-1.874121
O	-0.273821	-2.977290	-2.280879
O	-0.957068	-0.939632	-2.294934
H	-1.884750	-3.387808	-0.482313
H	-3.098153	-0.625407	-1.171200
H	-3.449601	-3.745558	1.318806
H	-6.610818	-0.817661	1.783493
H	-5.803329	-3.293559	2.653217
H	5.323595	-2.934400	-0.811234
H	4.407813	-3.532169	-2.213174
H	3.162781	-2.708012	0.568478
H	2.258022	-3.379277	-0.814722
H	2.500959	-2.179503	-3.168777
H	1.759460	-1.839696	-0.125782
H	1.911968	-0.732451	-2.377551
H	-0.590348	-1.776530	1.186171
H	-2.638625	0.488137	1.130850
H	-3.429687	1.803104	-1.005904
H	-3.446391	4.039264	-1.883767
H	-2.167153	4.566194	-0.790989
H	-1.859879	2.854841	-3.320191
H	0.030781	1.771171	-2.387213

H	0.181511	4.016972	-0.284679
H	-0.927784	4.294134	-2.887918
H	-2.835584	2.632782	0.438627
H	-1.733630	-1.327518	2.440515
H	0.010980	0.310149	-0.414196
H	2.550997	0.382683	0.812953
H	3.463304	-0.681607	-3.252365
H	1.232313	3.841715	-1.695051
H	5.451720	-2.110870	-2.386899
H	1.239610	2.202269	0.754849
C	0.086375	-0.179728	2.437181
C	2.202327	1.179278	3.698577
C	-0.064050	1.139962	2.872895
C	1.310926	-0.806983	2.668276
C	2.363288	-0.137456	3.286084
C	0.979653	1.811863	3.499695
H	-1.013790	1.655922	2.719805
H	1.456776	-1.836453	2.338408
H	3.322316	-0.639880	3.410268
H	3.027906	1.710912	4.171471
H	0.837656	2.840920	3.832669

H-bonded product-major-SR-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3706396 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.525118 Hartree
Entropy	0.000337 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.624621 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.0800

In(Qvib)	33.8792
ZPE	0.592055 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.625565 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP
SCF energy -1966.28312483 Hartree

Cartesian coordinates

N	1.774257	-0.135299	-1.773382
C	3.149547	-0.359044	-2.149974
C	3.452717	0.846539	-3.028643
C	2.136551	1.072576	-3.765176
C	1.041509	0.619404	-2.786067
C	-0.060032	-0.137758	-3.545197
N	-1.140752	-0.643827	-2.735490
C	-1.955641	0.178874	-2.030409
O	-2.028993	1.371779	-2.193521
N	-2.704106	-0.487391	-1.050301
S	-3.154048	0.436050	0.291390
O	-2.115458	0.251732	1.349433
C	-4.616183	-0.568452	0.828589
C	-4.199124	-1.980772	1.207342
C	-5.141292	0.183444	2.051874
C	-5.635093	-0.540999	-0.302413
C	1.153537	-0.664220	-0.658427
C	1.905807	-0.618716	0.683752
C	1.537205	0.661063	1.449244
C	2.996678	-1.628887	4.752723
C	1.722543	-1.418938	5.164608
C	0.914729	-1.506659	3.989258
C	1.769256	-1.766143	2.964587
O	3.027685	-1.838927	3.427668
C	1.584065	-1.916884	1.494865
C	0.217266	-2.434924	1.184077
N	-0.126069	-2.545344	-0.053532
O	-1.167251	-3.001958	-0.537102
O	0.784785	-2.081587	-0.946933
H	-0.505850	-2.765604	1.925062
H	2.305967	-2.681371	1.151869
H	-0.159579	-1.364044	3.914391
H	3.947708	-1.664243	5.277084
H	1.392104	-1.224623	6.180462
H	-3.387601	-1.974249	1.947723
H	-5.055614	-2.507440	1.655196
H	-4.400512	0.213668	2.862362
H	-6.040666	-0.320198	2.435672
H	-6.581295	-0.984149	0.043110
H	-5.422626	1.218714	1.806524
H	-5.854115	0.486268	-0.630964
H	2.140153	0.709370	2.367174

H	2.990588	-0.621642	0.509272
H	3.811414	-0.407492	-1.273656
H	3.688510	1.712339	-2.393630
H	4.302003	0.682156	-3.705732
H	1.996020	2.115048	-4.078956
H	0.578843	1.495460	-2.305584
H	0.376307	-0.999735	-4.070088
H	2.105598	0.457367	-4.679132
H	3.291099	-1.306095	-2.706678
H	0.485863	0.602379	1.768715
H	0.193481	-0.143168	-0.509945
H	-2.430805	-1.454050	-0.841662
H	-5.295100	-1.109339	-1.177563
H	-0.455911	0.539052	-4.318873
H	-3.871448	-2.577151	0.344967
H	-1.093729	-1.617953	-2.471095
C	1.750772	1.923960	0.658333
C	2.150825	4.254785	-0.845708
C	0.668684	2.625706	0.130391
C	3.036973	2.418476	0.436172
C	3.238030	3.573066	-0.307514
C	0.865948	3.779227	-0.620798
H	-0.344584	2.263138	0.309555
H	3.897771	1.895256	0.859559
H	4.250356	3.947465	-0.465682
H	2.307082	5.161563	-1.430897
H	0.003241	4.303252	-1.032881

H-bonded product-minor-SR-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3593467 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.523767 Hartree
Entropy	0.00034 Hartree
Inner energy	0.624072 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343

In(Qrot)	17.2079
In(Qvib)	34.2804
ZPE	0.591203 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.625017 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP
SCF energy -1966.27014037 Hartree

Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.616065	1.457813	-1.067225
C	-2.947891	2.049544	-0.990728
C	-3.162404	2.711351	-2.346808
C	-1.768672	3.227443	-2.678564
C	-0.813476	2.198592	-2.049833
C	0.392350	2.894999	-1.416514
N	1.288159	2.016402	-0.710578
C	2.100672	1.152231	-1.368911
O	2.241416	1.119880	-2.563832
N	2.789531	0.279321	-0.520028
S	3.096256	-1.295577	-1.068644
O	2.259456	-2.214960	-0.249042
C	4.830300	-1.477819	-0.439588
C	4.877594	-1.286016	1.067503
C	5.217437	-2.906253	-0.818309
C	5.684686	-0.461553	-1.184469
C	-1.433657	0.061073	-1.000985
C	-2.037956	-0.604612	0.255964
C	-0.972868	-0.958174	1.294163
C	-4.092551	-3.825407	2.565547
C	-5.075146	-2.892503	2.620429
C	-4.782678	-1.962692	1.576727
C	-3.646490	-2.410731	0.976743
O	-3.233195	-3.536833	1.578344
C	-2.828602	-1.874042	-0.150590
C	-3.700771	-1.550594	-1.320118
N	-3.187214	-0.918146	-2.329683
O	-3.705003	-0.584941	-3.373715
O	-1.846672	-0.645370	-2.212836
H	-4.755649	-1.805622	-1.390516
H	-2.098881	-2.654470	-0.436802
H	-5.349864	-1.076218	1.305887
H	-3.889477	-4.721266	3.145823
H	-5.910172	-2.868306	3.314111
H	4.176929	-1.958038	1.582711
H	5.888391	-1.514952	1.438359
H	4.581452	-3.648342	-0.317425
H	6.259197	-3.098082	-0.521609
H	6.746818	-0.625198	-0.946899
H	5.149737	-3.073727	-1.903943
H	5.571941	-0.553160	-2.275121

H	-0.261370	-1.671662	0.848455
H	-2.769610	0.078050	0.712587
H	-3.725792	1.310938	-0.757529
H	-3.484438	1.960730	-3.080760
H	-3.923167	3.503931	-2.320432
H	-1.596117	3.341115	-3.756709
H	-0.449989	1.510905	-2.828785
H	0.041883	3.646583	-0.693508
H	-1.611847	4.220450	-2.224801
H	-2.986247	2.805961	-0.183322
H	-1.464912	-1.503717	2.116457
H	-0.357327	-0.153091	-1.030359
H	2.618953	0.351262	0.480903
H	5.431974	0.570402	-0.907417
H	0.945501	3.435618	-2.199104
H	4.658187	-0.249151	1.361262
H	1.085196	1.858948	0.266345
C	-0.193452	0.173587	1.912943
C	1.320582	2.189300	3.163698
C	-0.721221	1.450377	2.107926
C	1.102449	-0.077470	2.374569
C	1.852624	0.915586	2.994798
C	0.028688	2.448177	2.722958
H	-1.728990	1.686476	1.769334
H	1.528959	-1.072343	2.232771
H	2.859951	0.691001	3.349025
H	1.906929	2.973350	3.642965
H	-0.404264	3.440142	2.856533

H-bonded-product-major-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/Def2-SV(P)
 SFC energy -1961.3635364 Hartree

Chemical potential	0.526896 Hartree
Entropy	0.000326 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.623136 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.1413
In(Qvib)	31.0628
ZPE	0.591231 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.624080 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/Def2-TZVP

SCF energy -1966.27427535 Hartree

Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.295175	1.029443	-1.846941
C	-2.566786	1.573847	-2.263723
C	-2.906233	0.724989	-3.480299
C	-1.544986	0.507768	-4.130046
C	-0.550430	0.448706	-2.961923
C	0.760447	1.148797	-3.342713
N	1.791224	1.134502	-2.336819
C	2.418810	-0.007129	-1.956587
O	2.288071	-1.070910	-2.511994
N	3.204920	0.149971	-0.819200
S	4.283238	-1.073079	-0.353763
O	5.668064	-0.570951	-0.495999
C	3.921339	-1.041069	1.473128
C	2.455635	-1.399785	1.667576
C	4.827899	-2.130874	2.043227
C	4.273776	0.315269	2.063127
C	-0.750089	1.138371	-0.584851
C	-1.680296	0.911987	0.621262
C	-1.608668	-0.556902	1.062325
C	-3.326664	1.130972	4.579155
C	-2.174215	0.710429	5.154291
C	-1.149972	0.942996	4.184952
C	-1.768945	1.488071	3.104199
O	-3.085098	1.600308	3.345074
C	-1.302272	1.914300	1.756068
C	0.163786	2.201741	1.756890
N	0.721426	2.520469	0.632983
O	1.879656	2.854971	0.407559
O	-0.106247	2.477490	-0.444777
H	0.797042	2.227143	2.640489
H	-1.823787	2.860101	1.515080
H	-0.092239	0.719094	4.286092
H	-4.356897	1.162898	4.922894
H	-2.060086	0.288423	6.148127
H	2.187752	-2.332477	1.147422
H	2.244477	-1.551037	2.737416
H	4.613895	-3.115340	1.599472

H	4.669068	-2.216991	3.128586
H	4.216685	0.268047	3.161773
H	5.889354	-1.904757	1.874952
H	5.297313	0.612495	1.796658
H	-2.308390	-0.717134	1.894946
H	-2.719763	1.133603	0.343433
H	-3.329941	1.486974	-1.477099
H	-3.331411	-0.234196	-3.150788
H	-3.632857	1.205313	-4.149571
H	-1.501405	-0.397793	-4.748703
H	-0.313704	-0.600130	-2.721985
H	0.560276	2.202348	-3.585866
H	-1.303001	1.357209	-4.789868
H	-2.504327	2.646946	-2.529357
H	-0.605337	-0.771120	1.463980
H	0.086517	0.422166	-0.508063
H	3.335679	1.078465	-0.424321
H	3.585490	1.110577	1.740875
H	1.133856	0.674014	-4.263585
H	1.789730	-0.604861	1.304808
H	1.922834	1.975277	-1.792690
C	-1.933072	-1.526136	-0.043747
C	-2.559438	-3.277239	-2.141578
C	-0.932935	-2.238291	-0.702107
C	-3.256473	-1.716845	-0.444662
C	-3.569349	-2.583114	-1.482643
C	-1.240327	-3.104087	-1.745870
H	0.111222	-2.113302	-0.409186
H	-4.058830	-1.183229	0.070176
H	-4.610115	-2.721919	-1.777820
H	-2.803471	-3.957966	-2.957604
H	-0.436150	-3.638227	-2.252344

H-bonded-product-major2-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3558144 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.524979 Hartree
Entropy	0.000338 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.624800 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.1777
In(Qvib)	34.0836
ZPE	0.592201 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.625744 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.26861183 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.325373	0.678216	-1.142194
C	-2.706558	1.042156	-1.369006
C	-3.198974	-0.045460	-2.318269
C	-1.984543	-0.291519	-3.215604
C	-0.761699	0.122511	-2.366185
C	0.128899	1.115661	-3.127857
N	1.168595	1.694651	-2.320180
C	2.205441	0.936784	-1.880865
O	2.477222	-0.150121	-2.327175
N	2.952718	1.543796	-0.866643
S	3.643997	0.700408	0.442181
O	2.779492	-0.427676	0.872882
C	5.197647	-0.049224	-0.271885
C	5.782564	0.886203	-1.318045
C	6.106257	-0.113182	0.960667
C	4.946027	-1.447127	-0.810906
C	-0.722310	0.432640	0.094951
C	-1.649678	0.185415	1.288578
C	-1.020154	-0.830618	2.255474
C	-5.207011	1.019547	3.438744
C	-5.615421	1.992420	2.589616
C	-4.445194	2.401412	1.876682
C	-3.423804	1.642505	2.357924
O	-3.888405	0.807927	3.301461
C	-1.975142	1.530841	2.018732
C	-1.525193	2.741084	1.262971
N	-0.433629	2.708191	0.571774
O	0.122619	3.617616	-0.035429
O	0.193808	1.508782	0.515233
H	-2.029814	3.703030	1.313698
H	-4.382344	3.161690	1.104080
H	-5.726074	0.414433	4.176986
H	-6.624140	2.379205	2.480992
H	5.857864	1.922782	-0.956602
H	6.801301	0.553329	-1.569977
H	6.334343	0.885614	1.361170

H	7.059847	-0.590650	0.690868
H	5.910764	-1.888578	-1.107136
H	5.657011	-0.711167	1.767482
H	4.498505	-2.099095	-0.049836
H	-1.606696	-0.835025	3.186186
H	-2.587705	-0.253563	0.921206
H	-3.287099	1.094490	-0.439887
H	-3.442684	-0.949974	-1.739727
H	-4.099637	0.239889	-2.879289
H	-1.914220	-1.333709	-3.552437
H	-0.147581	-0.754758	-2.107913
H	-0.485659	1.944621	-3.510271
H	-2.047034	0.327649	-4.124229
H	-2.789643	2.040248	-1.838780
H	-0.003335	-0.501041	2.518935
H	-0.003773	-0.392034	-0.009721
H	2.589262	2.429557	-0.529175
H	4.283982	-1.437637	-1.682132
H	0.563259	0.611899	-4.003902
H	5.189935	0.886911	-2.240861
H	0.895517	2.500402	-1.770070
C	-0.986809	-2.220996	1.678801
C	-0.990566	-4.776416	0.530097
C	0.183417	-2.761944	1.147071
C	-2.156783	-2.982363	1.630822
C	-2.161648	-4.248820	1.063459
C	0.178982	-4.029936	0.574675
H	1.110862	-2.186632	1.175359
H	-3.079721	-2.577698	2.053204
H	-3.084051	-4.830466	1.041319
H	-0.990940	-5.771470	0.083900
H	1.103594	-4.433725	0.161016
H	-1.412787	1.518004	2.972792

H-bonded-product-minor-SS-cat

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-1961.3594854 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.522772 Hartree
Entropy	0.000342 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.623820 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.9343
In(Qrot)	17.1991
In(Qvib)	34.9254
ZPE	0.590809 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.624764 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-1966.26982049 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

N	-1.113229	1.713613	-0.718225
C	-2.354919	2.448083	-0.487571
C	-2.111188	3.805131	-1.136518
C	-1.206529	3.453548	-2.310349
C	-0.280011	2.393064	-1.719530
C	0.975406	3.005315	-1.090943
N	1.786343	2.036940	-0.401791
C	2.672458	1.248161	-1.068418
O	3.052814	1.452164	-2.195043
N	3.086276	0.143102	-0.343645
S	4.481382	-0.733764	-0.771215
O	5.118326	-1.093888	0.522080
C	3.687986	-2.292292	-1.398653
C	4.871822	-3.186504	-1.762540
C	2.839776	-2.921258	-0.307727
C	2.871109	-1.935692	-2.632720
C	-1.039486	0.308942	-0.645229
C	-1.819190	-0.310499	0.536498

C	-0.898914	-0.929828	1.588841
C	-4.693381	-3.081791	2.523420
C	-5.458140	-1.962405	2.548415
C	-4.890803	-1.085289	1.574414
C	-3.830074	-1.748280	1.039439
O	-3.713857	-2.954498	1.616711
C	-2.824445	-1.366966	0.004801
C	-3.497044	-0.835351	-1.220673
N	-2.763230	-0.306612	-2.150709
O	-3.081955	0.195976	-3.205150
O	-1.412478	-0.358361	-1.886852
H	-4.572641	-0.833751	-1.381562
H	-2.254922	-2.278425	-0.256806
H	-5.232468	-0.089615	1.305161
H	-4.732430	-4.017203	3.074841
H	-6.323500	-1.780994	3.178668
H	5.489928	-3.424792	-0.886339
H	4.504837	-4.133466	-2.185374
H	3.413193	-3.065911	0.618528
H	2.479706	-3.907813	-0.637285
H	2.523720	-2.858370	-3.122154
H	1.952315	-2.311398	-0.083658
H	1.981110	-1.340723	-2.387419
H	-0.385232	-1.798672	1.146924
H	-2.424338	0.469218	1.018626
H	-3.234401	1.973360	-0.953363
H	-3.047853	4.293178	-1.436346
H	-1.602901	4.486361	-0.436584
H	-1.799594	3.010734	-3.123869
H	0.038383	1.686458	-2.500808
H	0.698051	3.788317	-0.369256
H	-0.664002	4.315193	-2.724542
H	-2.579665	2.551322	0.587441
H	-1.525274	-1.340017	2.398520
H	0.017157	0.008324	-0.591449
H	2.781774	0.005587	0.617140
H	3.458135	-1.368254	-3.369050
H	1.579144	3.485727	-1.872857
H	5.517863	-2.718796	-2.521298
H	1.497073	1.783467	0.532362
C	0.131712	-0.016419	2.201473
C	2.088687	1.619786	3.386802
C	-0.142821	1.315481	2.517213
C	1.400581	-0.513303	2.509227
C	2.373844	0.291988	3.092512
C	0.824559	2.124280	3.103863
H	-1.123079	1.740693	2.301736
H	1.637949	-1.554922	2.283869
H	3.363360	-0.119354	3.294235
H	2.849610	2.259269	3.833821

H 0.587907 3.163096 3.335939

Isolated RR-product

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-933.4607713 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.237089 Hartree
Entropy	0.000226 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.303608 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.0204
In(Qrot)	15.4418
In(Qvib)	17.7625
ZPE	0.286399 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.304552 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-936.12893716 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

C	2.344567	0.868390	-0.980698
C	0.909937	0.435612	-1.154957
C	0.009146	1.606079	-0.674345
C	-2.659302	-2.389883	-0.243311
C	-2.882729	-1.836520	-1.460375
C	-1.685564	-1.129666	-1.788678
C	-0.839356	-1.307264	-0.738596
O	-1.431206	-2.074838	0.191674
C	0.577036	-0.903517	-0.484469
C	1.513526	-2.079569	-0.818845
N	1.443003	-2.456420	-2.258362
O	0.929736	-3.496941	-2.544207
O	1.899902	-1.670347	-3.045962
H	1.217422	-2.962361	-0.242198
H	0.701851	-0.769683	0.602784
H	-1.486436	-0.568057	-2.696955
H	-3.266757	-3.010407	0.409835

H	-3.784761	-1.921796	-2.058531
H	-0.996430	1.463228	-1.089495
H	0.388664	2.535837	-1.128736
H	2.624006	1.735898	-1.631038
C	-0.081132	1.762869	0.819401
C	-0.244033	1.999267	3.608114
C	0.924794	2.404811	1.542491
C	-1.176789	1.254262	1.517519
C	-1.258314	1.368567	2.899614
C	0.846824	2.520989	2.923933
H	1.783651	2.833071	1.023027
H	-1.985483	0.767383	0.969560
H	-2.124159	0.964447	3.424923
H	-0.306135	2.090623	4.692806
H	1.643962	3.027280	3.468997
O	3.135758	0.406128	-0.215197
H	2.558899	-1.838480	-0.595842
H	0.755902	0.371109	-2.243983

Isolated SR-product

Geometry optimization, frequency calculation: PBEh-3c/def2-SV(P)

SFC energy	-933.4598453 Hartree
Chemical potential	0.239000 Hartree
Entropy	0.000220 Hartree/K
Inner energy	0.303533 Hartree
In(Qtrans)	19.0204
In(Qrot)	15.4157
In(Qvib)	15.7766
ZPE	0.286411 Hartree
Enthalpy	0.304478 Hartree

Single point energy: M06-2X/def2-TZVP

SCF energy	-936.12811706 Hartree
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Cartesian coordinates

C	1.666760	-0.329502	-2.389405
C	1.600217	0.019887	-0.922565
C	0.943087	1.393067	-0.689739
C	2.493459	-0.224820	3.155223
C	1.209930	-0.252945	3.586807
C	0.424772	-0.619810	2.449376
C	1.302026	-0.788576	1.423192
O	2.551538	-0.546335	1.853489
C	1.144484	-1.147109	-0.019155
C	-0.267290	-1.651880	-0.292341
N	-0.552078	-2.928157	0.445873
O	-1.648649	-3.048960	0.913500
O	0.311844	-3.754735	0.487317
H	-0.396957	-1.899185	-1.353868
H	1.827073	-1.982842	-0.241264
H	-0.652493	-0.752091	2.419096
H	3.436539	-0.007263	3.649111
H	0.857219	-0.046166	4.592638
H	1.426151	2.115047	-1.369910
H	2.668747	0.183027	-0.680017
H	1.202228	1.730459	0.322812
H	2.005144	0.525213	-3.031539
C	-0.550733	1.453435	-0.866977
C	-3.340035	1.495778	-1.157348
C	-1.380951	1.687900	0.228739
C	-1.142848	1.263845	-2.116392
C	-2.523925	1.280007	-2.261247
C	-2.763204	1.707324	0.088170
H	-0.935497	1.846643	1.212241
H	-0.524314	1.106630	-3.002086
H	-2.965632	1.125043	-3.245964
H	-4.424314	1.505034	-1.269850
H	-3.393359	1.886956	0.959608
O	1.443630	-1.397311	-2.873360
H	-1.052667	-0.947411	-0.004465

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